

PROCESS MONITORING FOR DEFECT CONTROL – FROM RTM TO SANDWICH PANEL CO-CURE

Steven Nutt, M. Anders, and T. Centea

M.C. Gill Composites Center, University of Southern California
3651 Watt Way-VHE-406, Los Angeles, CA, 90089, USA
Email: nutt@usc.edu, web page: <https://composites.usc.edu>

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ABSTRACT

Insights into process phenomena provide understanding necessary to eliminate manufacturing defects, yet process hardware (autoclaves, moulds, and tools), renders these phenomena opaque. At USC, we have developed instrumented testbeds that replicate common process conditions and afford real-time observation and insights into key phenomena leading to defects. In one example, a lab-scale RTM mould features a transparent window, allowing observation of mould filling and porosity evolution. In a second example, a pressurized cavity replicates autoclave conditions for co-cure of honeycomb panels, providing real-time observations of bond-line formation at core-skin junctions. Such observations were used to support the construction and validation of physics-based process models for co-cure. The combination of conventional systematic characterization of resin properties with the instrumented testbeds provide a method for process optimization, understanding of defect formation, and a basis for developing strategies for defect reduction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing defects cause variations in performance levels that lead to knockdowns in property levels used for design. The opacity of production hardware – autoclaves, tooling, and moulds – prevent direct observation of defect formation. As a result, attempts to understand defect origins rely primarily on “post-mortem” analysis of polished sections, leaving ample room for speculation and imagination, but providing scant guidance to adjust process parameters. Instrumented testbeds provide useful insights into defect formation mechanisms, and when combined with resin characterization tools – primarily thermal analysis and rheometry – constitute a framework for analyzing and mitigating defects.

In this work, two case studies are presented that illustrate a methodology that relies on conventional materials characterization complemented by data and observations acquired from lab-scale testbeds that replicate manufacturing conditions. The thermal analysis and rheological data can be presented alongside video observations on a synchronized time axis. Thus, the physical state of the resin (degree of cure, viscosity) can be correlated with flow phenomena, void nucleation, and other phenomena. The combined use of conventional and customized analytical tools provide rich datasets and useful insights into how, when, and where defects arise. These insights can be used to develop and validate process models, and to guide parametric adjustments to reduce/eliminate defects.

The first case study involves an effort to develop a benoxazine-epoxy formulation for liquid molding, specifically for RTM¹. The formulation included a solvent(s), and increasing the risk of void formation if volatiles left the solution during molding. A lab-scale RTM mold was designed and built to monitor the mold filling and curing processes directly, and the data acquired were combined with the use of a suite of conventional characterization tools, and led to specific recommendations for mitigating process-induced defects. The second case study focuses on co-cure of honeycomb sandwich panels, and attempts to develop physics-based models.² The name of the process derives from the simultaneous curing of facesheets and the film adhesive used to attach the core. Despite the appeal of a one-step process, the process is difficult to manage, and the facesheets prevent observation of bondline formation. A customized testbed was designed and built that afforded direct observation of the bondline during co-

cure under autoclave conditions.³ The project led to process models for co-cure and validation of predictions.

2 EXPERIMENT

The lab-scale RTM tool built for Case Study 1 (CS1) is shown in Figure 1 and described in detail in reference [1]. The main body of the mold was an anodized aluminum block containing inlet and outlet ports with “line injection” grooves used to generate a one-dimensional flow front. A “picture frame” plate with a rectangular cavity was placed against the main body to define the thickness (3.2 mm) and in-plane dimensions (76 × 127 mm) of the part. The second tool face was a 20 mm thick tempered glass plate, rated for pressures up to 1200 kPa. This glass plate formed a rigid window that afforded direct *in situ* observation of in-mold phenomena, including air evacuation, preform saturation during injection, and the time and location of any subsequent void formation.

Figure 1: Expanded view of lab-scale RTM tool.¹

For Case Study 2 (CS2), attention focused on co-cure of sandwich panels under autoclave conditions. The elements to be assembled included a honeycomb core (Nomex), a toughened epoxy film adhesive (Loctite EA 9658 AERO 060UNS, Henkel Corp.), and CF-epoxy prepreg plies (Syensco 5320-1 or Hexcel 8552S). To view phenomena associated with bond-line formation, a cell was designed that replicated autoclave pressure and temperature while affording direct observation of the bondline during co-cure. A half-panel sample was used (one face sheet, one adhesive film, and a core of half-thickness) in a testbed shown in Figure 2. Note that the glass viewport on the lower side allowed video observation of film adhesive redistribution during co-cure, a process called reticulation, that was intended to result in fillet formation at cell wall-facesheet junctions (adhesive remaining between cell walls amounted to parasitic weight).

The reticulation process – which can be performed in several ways [11,31] – results in adhesive located only along the edges of the honeycomb cell walls, with an opening in the film at the center of each cell. Fig. 4 shows the stages of adhesive reticulation. First, the adhesive film was placed onto the top side of the honeycomb core and manually perforated in the center of each honeycomb cell using a ~1mm diameter needle. Then, heated air was blown over the surface of the film using a handheld hot-air gun. As the film softened under the applied heat, surface tension caused the holes to

widen, reshaping the film into an adhesive bead along the edges of the cell walls. Temperatures were monitored using a thermocouple and did not exceed 70 °ΔC. Reticulation was completed in < 3 min, ensuring that the process did not advance the cure of the adhesive.

Figure 2: Section view of co-cure fixture with sample and consumables.³

Figure 3. Stages of adhesive reticulation process. Left: film applied to core and perforated. Center: Film softening and perforations expanding due to surface tension. Right: Process completed – adhesive forms a fillet along edges of cell walls.

Figure 4. Temperature cycle used for all tests (top left), and the two cycles used for autoclave and vacuum bag pressures. On right, diagram of Cases A-E, where the three axes denote the test variables.

The process parameters for CS 2 are summarized in Figure 4a. The temperature cycle resembles the manufacturer-recommended cure cycle for the prepreg. The three temperature stages – RT, 110C, and 177C, are labeled Stages I, II, and III. Three parameters were varied between cases – the initial adhesive format, the core breathability, and the imposed P_{auto} and P_{bag} pressure cycles. The five test cases are presented as a cube diagram in Figure 5a. Each of the three axes corresponds to one of the varied parameters. (1) The adhesive was applied either as a continuous film or reticulate onto the HC core. (2) The core cavity was either sealed or connected via the “core vent” to equilibrate the gas pressure in the core cavity with that of the vacuum bag. (3) Autoclave and vacuum bag pressures were applied according to either of two cycles – “simple” or “staged” – as shown in Fig. 4a.

5 RESULTS

For CS1, neat resin BOX-e samples were produced without entrapped air during injection. The test results are summarized in Figure 5 as a process map relating cure temperature, imposed mold pressure, and defect growth. Each point represents one sample. Temperature and pressure combinations that resulted in the generation of voids are shown in red, while samples that did not grow voids are shown in blue. In cases when voids did develop, they nucleated on the hottest side of the mold cavity (the tool side that contains the heating elements), grew rapidly, sometimes detached and floated upwards, and eventually were fixed in place when the resin gelled. Application of pressures of 200kPa were sufficient to suppress voids in molded plates of neat-resin.

Figure 5: Temperature-pressure map of neat-resin tests. Red (on graph) indicates conditions that lead to void growth, while blue corresponds to conditions that suppress void growth. Points correspond to individual tests and background shading is used to highlight the general trend.

While applied pressures $>200\text{kPa}$ sufficed to prevent bulk porosity, surface porosity developed, typically on the cooler side of the mold cavity (with the glass plate). The window in the mold afforded visual confirmation that, initially after injection, the surfaces of all samples were bubble-free. However, porosity developed on the window side during high-temperature dwells late in the cure cycle. The aluminum tool side (which was slightly hotter, since it contained the heating elements) had effectively no defects for all samples, and micrographs of polished cross-sections confirmed that internal porosity was also negligibly low. For this reason, only the quality of the cold sides is considered below.

In situ data and porosity formation mechanisms are revealed from the measured sensor data for a composite sample, shown in Figure 6, for formulation F1 cured under Cycle A, which resulted in 26% surface porosity. The temperature graph consists of the controller temperature (black) and the temperatures of the hot and cold sides of the mold cavity (in red and blue, respectively). The hot side,

being closest to the heating elements, followed the control temperature to within 1°C, while the cold side lagged by roughly 4 min (or, equivalently, 8°C) during ramps and stabilized at 4°C below the hot side at steady-state conditions during high-temperature dwell.

Figure 6: Temperature, viscosity, and pressure for formulation F1, Cycle A. Surface porosity measurements are shown at right, where the top row is formulation F1, Cycle A, the middle row is F2, Cycle A, and bottom row is F2, Cycle B. The thermocouple is visible in the first image.

Surface porosity occurred because of the relative timing of the pressure drop and the increasing viscosity at the coldest location of the mold cavity. The pressure drop occurred when the cold-side viscosity was in the vicinity of 100 Pa·s, which is past the gel point, but far below the critical value of 7×10^4 Pa·s that has been shown to suppress volatile release. The hot-side, meanwhile, had already reached a high viscosity level, and therefore did not off-gas. Once the mold cavity pressure decreased below the critical value, voids began to form at the cold surface. The period of void formation was clearly observable through the window in the mold, and is indicated on Fig. 6a.

Fig. 7 shows a series of images recorded in situ for the same sample, beginning with an initially defect-free surface just before the pressure drop. Almost immediately after the pressure fell below the critical value, voids began to form and continued to grow for 15 min. All void growth finally ceased as the cold-side viscosity reached the “safe” zone, where the resin was nearly vitrified. In cases of extreme porosity such as in Fig. 7, much of the surface separates from the tool face, clearly manifest through the window because of the change in refractive index (compare Fig. 7c and d), and accompanied by a concurrent spike/drop in measured cavity pressure (see Fig. 6 at 136 min). The volatile gasses are less dense than the liquid resin, so their release at the cold surface relieves the tensile stresses generated by cure shrinkage. This phenomenon can be seen in Fig. 6 by the gradual recovery in pressure during the time of porosity formation. Note that since the pressure drop occurred when most of the resin was already approaching high viscosities (and due to the presence of the fibrous preform), the total volume of volatiles released was much less than for the ambient-pressure neat resin samples (which began to grow bubbles earlier, during the ramp to the high-temperature dwell).

In summary, the tendency of this resin to exhibit surface porosity in RTM processing stems from a combination of two factors: significant potential for volatile release during cure, and rapid, highly temperature-dependent gelation, which increases the material sensitivity to in-mold temperature gradients. Additionally, the distribution of the porosity – concentrated on the cold surface – is determined by the direction of the temperature gradient. Additional information regarding process monitoring with the RTM testbed is included in reference [1].

Figure 7: Formation of surface porosity recorded *in situ* for the composite sample with formulation F1, Cycle A. Time labels correspond to the data in Fig. 6. The thermocouple used to measure the window-side temperature history is visible in the frame.

Figure 8: (a) Temperature data for the three cases using the “simple” pressure cycle (A, B, and C). Models for the glass transition temperature and viscosity (for both the prepreg resin and the adhesive) are shown, computed from the temperature history recorded outside the vacuum bag, near the center of the laminate. (b) *In situ* images of the bond-line during processing. Columns correspond to Cases A, B, and C (left to right), and rows correspond to the times of interest t_1 through t_4 indicated in (a).

CS2 entails the use of a similar approach to monitor defect evolution during co-cure of sandwich panels in an autoclave, with the expectation that the insights would provide a basis for a process model. Measured data for Cases A, B and C is shown in Fig. 8, and *in situ* images from these tests are shown in Fig. 8b. For Cases D and E, measured data and corresponding *in situ* images are shown in Figs. 9a and 9b, respectively. To fully appreciate the dynamic behavior captured in the visual data, readers are encouraged to view the timelapse videos from which the images in Figs. 8 and 9 were taken.¹

Case A. Figure 8(a) shows the measured temperatures (top) and pressures (middle) for Case A, which featured a continuous adhesive film, a sealed core, and the simple pressure cycle. Models were used to compute the glass transition temperature T_g of the prepreg and adhesive, as well as the viscosity μ profiles (bottom graph). The indicated times of interest t_1 through t_4 correspond to the images in the left column of Fig. 8(b).

Upon application of vacuum in the bag, P_{core} remained unchanged, and the continuous adhesive film acted as a barrier for gas transport. Negligible change was observed visually during Stage I, although flow occurred as the temperature was raised between t_1 and t_2 . First, prepreg resin (which appears clear, while the aluminum-powder-filled adhesive is gray) pushed through the adhesive film in a grid-like pattern, clearly emanating from the “pinholes” between the fiber tows in the fabric weave. Additionally, the mixture of adhesive and prepreg resin migrated toward the cell walls, forming fillets. During this period, P_{core} increased to ~ 200 kPa due to ideal gas law expansion (and likely some volatile generation). During the intermediate temperature dwell, little change was observed, and P_{core} decayed due to continual application of vacuum to the bag.

During the second temperature ramp (between t_3 and t_4), the adhesive fillets appeared to “inflate” and bubbles appeared in the locations where the prepreg resin had created discontinuities in the film adhesive. After t_4 , all motion abruptly ceased, as the adhesive had gelled. Note that during the second temperature ramp, the adhesive viscosity was already rapidly increasing, whereas the prepreg resin was just reaching its minimum viscosity. Thus, during this ramp, bubbles could still nucleate and grow within the prepreg resin. However, they became trapped by the adhesive film. The section view of the sample confirms that the fillet “inflation” was due to the growth and entrapment of bubbles between the adhesive film and the first ply of prepreg. P_{core} followed a similar trend during Stage III as in Stage II, first increasing during the ramp (although to a lesser extent), and decaying during the dwell.

Case A showed that the continuous adhesive film was disrupted by the behavior of the prepreg resin. Specifically, the mismatch in gel times was such that, during the second temperature ramp, the prepreg resin formed bubbles that distorted – and became trapped by – the rapidly gelling adhesive layer. To prevent the adhesive from acting as a barrier for gas transport, the film was reticulated onto the core in Case B.

Case B. Figure 8(a) shows P_{core} (all other temperatures and pressures were identical to Case A). The core evacuation during Stage I, in the absence of a continuous adhesive film, depended on the prepreg permeability. Initial evacuation was rapid, but halted as the skin compacted (analogous to the behavior observed by Kratz [20]). A new pathway for gas transport formed after ~ 45 min (the delay caused by gradual displacement of the highly viscous prepreg resin), allowing core evacuation to continue. During the remainder of the cycle, P_{core} followed a similar trend as in Case A, although shifted downward due to the lower initial pressure upon heating.

In Fig. 8 (Case B, t_1) the reticulated adhesive is visible along the edges of the cell walls, and the first prepreg ply is visible in the center of each cell. During the room-temperature vacuum hold, minor bubble formation was observed in the adhesive and prepreg resin. As the temperature was increased between t_1 and t_2 , the adhesive fillets formed, and a mixture of prepreg resin and bubbles could be seen pushing out from the pinholes in the fabric weave. By t_2 , most of the bubbles had disappeared, leaving a layer of resin at the skin/core interface and creating a continuous meniscus with the adhesive. During the dwell between t_2 and t_3 , bubbles gradually reappeared in the prepreg resin. During the final temperature ramp, the bubbles grew, yet none burst before resin gelation, resulting in a large cluster of bubbles at the center of each cell.

Contrasting this behavior to Case A reveals that the bubbles in the bond-line in Case A were not solely due to the adhesive acting as a barrier, but also a consequence of the core pressure. Even

without the barrier (i.e., Case B), P_{core} was low enough to allow bubble growth within the resin at the skin/core interface, yet not so low that the bubbles burst. Considering this insight, the modification for Case C was chosen to afford improved control over P_{core} .

Case C. Case C simulated the conditions of a vented sandwich structure – in which P_{core} can equilibrate with P_{bag} – by connecting the core vent to the vacuum line. During the room temperature vacuum hold, thin-walled bubbles grew from the pinholes in the fabric and burst, indicating that air initially trapped between the prepreg plies was evacuating into the core. Previously, in Cases A and B, vacuum was only applied on the upper surface of the skin, so air in the core had to travel upwards through the skin to escape. Conversely, in Case C, the core was evacuated directly and simultaneously with the vacuum bag, so air was not driven through the skin, and air initially entrapped within the skin could evacuate in either direction (up through the perforations in the release film, or down into the core), along the path of least resistance.

Upon initial heating, the vacuum in the core pulled a foamy mixture of gas and resin out from the fabric pinholes. Towards the end of the first ramp (see Fig. 8, t_2), vigorous frothing was observed, with large bubbles growing and bursting repeatedly. Bubble formation slowed during the intermediate-temperature dwell, but, by that point, much of the adhesive had been spattered onto the cell walls, leaving little at the skin/core interface to form fillets (see Fig. 8, t_3). Small bubbles remained along the edges of the cell walls against the skin, which grew during the second temperature ramp and became fixed at gelation (t_4). The section view of this sample provides a complementary perspective of the small, void-filled fillets and the adhesive coating the cell walls.

Case D. The staged pressure cycle used for Case D was designed to avoid the observed defect formation phenomena, by applying positive pressure within the vacuum bag to suppress the release of gasses that could not be evacuated prior to gelation. Stage I was identical to Case C: reticulated adhesive and full vacuum in the bag and core, to maximize air removal from the skin while the resin and adhesive were still at high viscosity (“equilibrated” P_{core} in Case D matched P_{bag} exactly (Fig. 9). During Stage II, to avoid the fillet disruption that occurred in Case C and duplicate the undisrupted flow seen in Case B, the vacuum bag was vented with N_2 to ~ 100 kPa. To prevent excess resin exuding toward the skin/core interface, P_{auto} was increased to only 205 kPa, maintaining the same compaction pressure ($P_{auto} - P_{bag}$) as in Stage I. Finally, in Stage III, recall that during the second temperature ramp in Cases A and B, a P_{core} range of ~ 50 – 150 kPa caused bubbles to grow yet remain sessile until gelation. In Case C, vacuum pressure in the core caused bubbles to burst, but this also caused severe fillet disruption. Therefore, in Case D, the opposite approach was used to prevent defects in Stage III: the application of positive pressure to suppress bubble formation and growth. First, P_{auto} was increased to 377 kPa to maintain compaction on the sample, and then P_{bag} was increased to 239 kPa.

Figure 9: Temperature and pressure data for the cases D and E, using the “staged” pressure cycle. Models for T_g and viscosity (for prepreg resin and adhesive) are computed from temperature history.

The images in the left column of Fig. 10 correspond to the times indicated on Fig. 9. During the initial vacuum hold, thin-walled bubbles similar to Case C appeared and burst, indicating air evacuation from the skin. During the temperature ramp and dwell of Stage II, fillet formation occurred, the flow undisrupted by bubbles (similar to Case B t_2 but without the bubble formation seen at ~ 50 kPa in Case B t_3). The image captured at t_3 for Case D (Fig. 10) was taken in the brief time after P_{auto} was increased, but before P_{core} was increased. Momentarily, resin containing small bubbles exuded from the fabric pinholes due to the increased compaction pressure. However, once the bag/core

pressure was set to the final value, the excess resin receded into the skin, and the bubbles disappeared. The equal gas pressures on the upper and lower boundaries of the skin (i.e. P_{bag} and P_{core} , respectively) resulted in a hydrostatic condition in which no gas was driven through the skin. Furthermore, the gas pressure in the core/bag imposed a lower bound for the resin pressure in the skin, which prevented the formation of bubbles. The resin and adhesive remained effectively motionless during the second temperature ramp and until gelation (t_4).

Figure 10: In situ images of the bond-line during processing. Columns correspond to Cases D and E (left to right), and rows (top to bottom) correspond to the times t_1 through t_4 indicated in Fig. 9.

CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated a methodology for understanding the origins of defects in composites, and controlling those defects through process modifications. The method relies on process monitoring through the use of instrumented testbeds that afford direct observation of process phenomena. These observations are closely coupled with systematic characterization of resin properties by more conventional methods, such as thermal analysis and rheology. Visual data acquired with these tools revealed the occurrence and timing of defect-formation mechanisms. For CS2, these included (a) gas entrapment by early gelation of the adhesive, (b) bond-line bubble growth at intermediate core pressure, and (c) fillet disruption from the bursting of bubbles at low core pressures. In CS1, the defect formation mechanisms during RTM included pore formation from volatile evolution, surface porosity from cure shrinkage, and the times and temperatures at which these occurred.

The case studies demonstrate the utility of *in situ* visualization for composites manufacturing (for both RTM and autoclave co-cure). Through visual observations, the process conditions corresponding

to defect formation can be identified, informed process modifications can be made, and theories about the relevant physical phenomena can be validated. Altogether, this approach can provide understanding and insight into manufacturing processes that could not be attained by traditional inspection of the structures after manufacturing. Most importantly, much of the guesswork can be eliminated from process troubleshooting, and the interactions between materials and phenomena can be analyzed in realistic conditions.

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